

CLINICAL EVALUATION OF AN INTEGRATIVE AYURVEDIC PROTOCOL IN THE MANAGEMENT OF AMLAPITTA

Dr. Apurva Gupta^{1*}, Dr. Nitin Mahajan², Dr. Radhika Gupta³

¹PG Scholar First Year Department of Kayachikitsa,

²Principal, HOD and Professor Department of Kayachikitsa,

³Assistant Professor Department of Kayachikitsa,

^{1,2,3}Jammu Institute of Ayurveda and Research Jammu and Kashmir.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Apurva Gupta

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ABSTRACT

Amlapitta is one of the most common diseases seen in the society. It is seen in all ages, all classes, and all community. *Amlapitta* correlated with Hyperacidity refers to a set of symptoms caused by an imbalance between the acid secreting mechanism of the stomach and proximal intestine and the protective mechanisms that ensure their safety. The stomach normally secretes acid that is essential in the digestive process. When there is excess production of acid in the stomach, it results in the condition known as Acidity. *Amlapitta* is managed through *Pitta Shaman* with *Vamana* and *Virechana* because according to our *Acharyas* it occurs due to vitiation of *Kapha Pitta Doshas*. Swamarg Chikitsa is described for the treatment of *Amlapitta*. In Ayurved, Hyperacidity can be explained under broad umbrella of *UrdwardAmlapitta*, *VidagdhaJeerna*, *Samapitta Laxanas*, *Pittaja Grahani* Lakshana. This marks improvement in symptoms such that retrosternal burning, acidity eructation, nausea, indigestion and flatuation. *Laghu Sutshekhara Rasa*, *Avipattikar Churna*, *Praval Panchamruta* along with lifestyle dietary modification provided significant relief in symptoms of *Amlapitta* with specific reference to Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD).

KEYWORDS: Gastroesophageal reflux disease; Acidity; *Agnimandya*; *Amlapitta*.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, *Amlapitta* is described as a *Pittaja Vikara* resulting from *Agnimandya* (impaired digestive fire) and *Aaharaja Hetu* (dietary causes). *Acharya Charaka* and *Kashyapa* have mentioned that improper eating habits like excessive intake of spicy, sour, and oily foods, irregular meal timings, and emotional stress are major causative factors. Modern science correlates *Amlapitta* with acid peptic disorders, including gastritis, dyspepsia, and reflux esophagitis. The modern line of management includes antacids and proton pump inhibitors, which provide symptomatic relief but often fail to address the root cause. *Ayurveda*, on the other hand, aims to restore the balance of *Agni* and *Pitta Dosha* through a holistic approach.

Urdhwaga Amlapitta: *Aruchi* (Anorexia),
Gurukoshthatva (Heavinessabdomen), *Gaurav*

(Lethargy), *Vibandha* (Constipation), *Shiroruja* (Headache), *Utklesh* (Nausea), *Tiktamlodgar* (acid eructation). *Urdhwaga Amlapitta* is mainly caused by intake of *Aharas* which is not suited to ones *Prakriti*. e faulty diet e.g *Amla* (sour), *Katu* (pungent), *Lavana* (salty), *Guru* (heavy meal), *Snigdha* (oily/excessive liquid), *Abhishandhi* (food that is difficult to digest) *Aharas*. Besides, addictions like smoking, alcohol, tobacco chewing, excessive stress, condiments also lead to *Urdhwaga Amlapitta*. Drugs like NSAID's, corticosteroids, also cause dyspepsia. Ayurveda physicians are treating dyspepsia since long time with the help of knowledge as given in classical *Ayurveda* text (causative factors, pathogenesis, treatment plan, and preventive tool) but there is a lack of evidence as per modern standards. Burning sensation, poor digestion, thirst, perspiration, nausea, sour or bitter belching, fevers due to vitiated pitta and kapha and heaviness. *Chhardi*

(vomiting), *Pittaja Gulma* (hard mass in the abdomen caused due to vitiated pitta), *Parinamshoola* (duodenal ulcer), *Pittashmari* (stones formed vitiated Pitta) and *Annadravashoola* (gastritis/peptic ulcer) are the most commonly seen symptoms in people with acidity.^[3]

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To study the clinical presentation of Amlapitta as per Ayurvedic and modern perspectives.
2. To assess the efficacy of Ayurvedic management in the treatment of Amlapitta.
3. To analyze the role of Pathya-Apathya (dietary regulation) and Aushadha-Sevana Kala in recovery.

CASE PROFILE

In this study, a 42 yrs /female patient with chief complaints of retrosternal burning, Acidic eruction, Nausea, Indigestion and Flatulence for 2 months, visited for ayurvedic managements. The patient was working in a private company and had history of eating too much spicy and fatty food, stress, tobacco chewing and drinking coffee in last 6 months.

History- No medical and surgical major past history.

Physical Examination

Temp=98, R/R=20, Pulse=80/min, BP=130/80 mm of mg, Weight =70 Kgs Per
Abdomen was soft, non-tender, no abnormality detected.

Ashtavidha Pariksha

- *Nadi* [Pulse] - 80/min
- *Mala* [stool] - *Asamyaka*[unsatisfactory bowel habit]
- *Jeevha* [Tongue] - *Saam*[Coated]. *Mutra* [Urine] - *Samyaka* [Clear]
- *Shabda* [Speech] - *Spashta*[Clear]
- *Sparsh* [Skin] - *Rukshatwam*
- *Druka* [Eyes] - *Prakruta* [no pallor no icterus]
- *Akruti*[posture] - *Heena*

Systemic Examination

- Respiratory system- On auscultation, normal bronchiovascular sounds heard and no abnormality detected.
- Cardiovascular system- S1 S2 heard and no abnormality detected.
- Central Nervous System- Higher mental function found to be normal.
- Diagnosis- Based on patients history, assessment of clinical feature and physical examination the final diagnosis made was *Amlapitta* with special reference to GERD.

Ayurveda Treatment for *Amlapitta*^[4]

According to *Acharya Charak Chikitsa* of all disease can be divided in 3 part

- *Nidanparivarjan*
- *Samshodhana*
- *Shamana*.

Nidana Parivarjana

The therapy of *Nidana Parivarjana* aims at avoiding the causes of disease. It is recommended as the primary treatment for many diseases. *Nidana Parivarjana* helps stop the progression of a disease and avoids relapse. Withdrawal of the aetiological factors of the disease is called *Nidana Parivarjana* as the first line of treatment of all the diseases. In *Amlapitta* excessive *Nidana Sevana* leads to *Mandagni* and *Pitta Vriddhi*. So *Nidan* of *Amlapitta* should be removed in its first treatment.

Ruksha Annapana (consuming dry foods), *Langhana* (fasting) and *Vatika Annapana* (consuming a diet that aggravates Vata in the body) are some of the causes that should be avoided in case of acidity.

Faulty dietary habits, excessive sexual indulgence, excess mental and physical work, consuming alcoholic beverages and consuming excessive amounts of rice and beans are some of the *Nidanas* (causes) of *Amlapitta*. *Adhyasana* (eating too soon after a meal) should also be avoided to prevent Acidity.

Shodhana

Ayurveda uses the following *shodhana* therapies for acidity treatment. *Samshoshana* karma eliminates the vitiated Doshas from their root cause and thus cures the disease entirely so that there is least probability of recurrence of disease. *Acharya Kashyap* has mentioned *Amlapitta* is developed from *Amashaya* (stomach) and *kapha* and *Pitta Dosha* are having *Ashrayas*. *Vamana* and *Virechana* karma as the best treatment for *Amlapitta*, for an example as if we cut down the root of any tree, the stem of the tree dies automatically.

Shamana

The following *Shamana* therapies are used for the treatment of acidity.

Langhana

Langhana therapy brings lightness in the body as it creates a balance between the *Doshas* and *Dhatu*. *Langhana* is mentioned as the first line of treatment for diseases originating in the stomach and caused by vitiation of the *Rasa Dhatu*. *Nirahara* (abstaining from food) and *Phalahara* (consuming only fruits) are two types of fasting methods practiced in *Langhana* therapy. *Langhana* therapy provides relief from *Chhardi*, *Atisara* (diarrhoea) and *Arochaka* (indigestion); therefore, it is beneficial in treating acidity. It improves the digestive fire and provides nourishment to the body. *Langhana* also reduces constipation and is beneficial in treating skin and urinary disorders, stiffness in the thighs, and abscess.

Oral Medications	Dose	Duration
• <i>Avipattikar Churna</i>	1 tsp. <i>Pragbhakta</i>	1 month
• <i>Laghusutshekhara Rasa</i>	2 tab. <i>Abhakta, Adhobhakta</i>	1 month
• <i>Pravala Panchamrut Rasa</i>	2 tab. <i>Abhakta, Adhobhakta</i>	1 month
• <i>Patoladi Kadha</i>	4 tsp. <i>Pragbhakta</i>	1 month
• <i>Ushirasava-</i>	4 tsp. <i>Pragbhakta</i>	1 month

Pravala Panchamrita Rasa

The formulation of *Pravala Panchamrita Rasa* consists of five ingredients including *Pravala Bhasma*, *Mauktik Bhasma* (calcined of shell), *Shankha Bhasma* (calcined pearl), *Shauktik Bhasma* (calcined preparation acidity, ascites and pain caused due to *Pitta*).

Laghusutashekhara Rasa

Sutashekhara Rasa has an antacid and anticholinergic effect in the body and is commonly used for the treatment of acidity in *Ayurveda*. It primarily acts on *Pitta Dosh*

and provides relief from many symptoms including abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, epigastric tenderness, heartburn, fevers, headaches and breathing troubles.

Avipattikar Churna

Avipattikar Churna is an Ayurvedic formulation including *Musta* (nutgrass), *Vidanga* (false black pepper), *Ela*, *Lavanga* (clove), *Trikatu* (a combination of the three acids – *Pippali*, *Shunthi*, and *Maricha*) and other ingredients. It is mainly indicated for acidity treatment in *Ayurveda*.

Follow-up and Outcomes

Day	Observation
Day 15	Appetite improved, reduction in burning sensation in chest,
Day 30	Patient reported almost complete relief from burning sensation and sour eructations, Appetite normalized

DISCUSSION

Amlapitta is a *Pitta* dominant disease in association with *Kapha* and *Vata Dosh*. Excess formation of vitiated *Pitta* is the main pathological mechanism behind manifestation of this disease. The *Pitta* gets vitiated due to improper dietary and lifestyle habits. The drugs that have *Tikta-Madhura Rasa* (bitter-sweet taste), *Madhura Vipaka* (post digestive effect in sweet taste), *SheetaVirya* (cooling energy of substance), *Laghu* (light), *Ruksha Guna* (dry) and pacifies to *Pitta-Kapha* properties are beneficial in the management of *Amlapitta*. Numerous herbal and herbomineral formulations are mentioned in Ayurvedic classics for the management of *Amlapitta*.

The observation revealed that, this specific treatment which *Laghusutshekhara Rasa*, *Amalaki Churna*, *Pravala Panchamrut Rasa*, *Avipattikar Churna* is significant relief in the management of symptoms *Amlapitta* and no adverse effect of medicine. This Ayurvedic combination treatment proved an effective alternative treatment in the management of *Amlapitta*.

Amlapitta is a psychosomatic disorder, where psychological factors play an equally important factor along with the dietary indiscretion. Principle of *Ashta Ahar Vidhi Visheshayatana* and *Dashvidh AharVidhi Vidhan* mentioned in *Charak Samhita* are most important aspect for preventive and curative aspect of health. They are to be examined before food intake and are to be followed during food intake. The *Samprapti* of *Amlapitta*, the normal function of *Amla Rasa* are basically attributed to *Pitta Dosa*. *Amla Rasa* and *Amla Vipaka* plays important role in the pathogenesis of *Amlapitta*. *Dosha*, *Dushya*, *Strotas*, *Adhistan*, *Agni*,

Ama are basic component of any disease process and also *Amlapitta*.

CONCLUSION

As we can see now a days people are very busy in their life so they have to take instants, oily and fermented food and do not live a healthy life so they have to suffer hyperacidity. In this way through Ayurveda we can manage effectively *Amlapitta* with follow *Dincharya* and *Rutucharya* rules and some *Shodhan Shaman Chikista*.

REFERENCE

1. A Textbook of Kayachikitsa, Prof. Vaidya. Y. G. Joshi, Pune Sahitya Mandal Vitaran, 479.
2. A Textbook of Kayachikitsa, Prof. Vaidya. Y. G. Joshi, Pune Sahitya Mandal Vitaran, 481.
3. A Textbook of Kayachikitsa, Prof. Vaidya. Y. G. Joshi, Pune Sahitya Mandal Vitaran, 482.
4. A Textbook of Kayachikitsa, Prof. Vaidya. Y. G. Joshi, Pune Sahitya Mandal Vitaran, 483.
5. Madhavanidanam, Rogaviniscaya of Madhavakara, Prof. K.R. Srikantha Murthy, Publisher- Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, Fourth Edition, 2001.
6. Bhaishajya Ratnavali of Prof. Siddhinandan Mishra, Publisher— Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 239.
7. Bhaishajya Ratnavali of Prof. Siddhinandan Mishra, Publisher— Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 1126.
8. Bhaishajya Ratnavali of Prof. Siddhinandan Mishra, Publisher— Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 1127.
9. Bhaishajya Ratnavali of Prof. Siddhinandan Mishra, Publisher— Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 58.

10. Bhaishajya Ratnavali of Prof. Siddhinandan Mishra, Publisher-- Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 658.
11. BhaishajyaRatnavali of Prof. Siddhinandan Mishra, Publisher— Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 513.
12. Bhaishajya Ratnavali of Prof. Siddhinandan Mishra, Publisher— Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 90313. www.wedmd.com.